

Caves, K. & Oswald-Egg, M.E. (2019). Storming and forming. Implementing a new dual VET law in Serbia. In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.322-327) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641057>

Storming and forming. Implementing a new dual VET law in Serbia

Caves, Katherine

KOF Swiss Economic Institute, ETH Zurich, Switzerland, caves@kof.ethz.ch

Oswald-Egg, Maria Esther

KOF Swiss Economic Institute, ETH Zurich, Switzerland, egg@kof.ethz.ch

1 Introduction

Serbia is implementing a new dual vocational education and training (VET) law as part of its efforts to improve its VET system. The law includes a transitional article that allows the law to be adjusted after three years (starting in 2018) to remedy any problems discovered in initial implementation. This research project uses the implementation of Serbia’s dual VET law to explore the influencing factors for implementing system-level VET reforms.

Our main research question is “what enables and/or prevents implementation of the Serbian dual VET law?” The secondary question addresses the implications of the first, asking, “What changes to the Serbian dual VET law would facilitate implementation?” In this way, the project addresses both theory and practice.

Caves and Baumann (2018) reviewed the literature on implementing VET reforms and found that factors in a six-category framework affect implementation progress, shown in Figure 1. The factors affecting VET are different from those affecting general education reform—visible most notably in the key role of employers and intermediaries—and still not completely clear. This research project aims to clarify the roles, relationships, and behavior of those factors through an in-depth analysis of the Serbian reform case.

Source: Caves & Baumann (2018)

Figure 1 Factors affecting VET implementation

We further contribute to theory by identifying key factors for specific points in the implementation process and by doing so in a transitional economy. This paper deals with the first year of implementation, and we expect that the key factors will be different for early implementation challenges than they will be for the issues that arise later in the process. This is the case for general education reform (i.e. Fullan, 2015) as well as general policy implementation (i.e. Nilsen, 2015). In addition, Serbia is a transitional economy¹ so what we learn here can apply to the many countries using improved VET to drive development.

2 Method & Data

We follow a two-step process of document analysis and informal interviews followed by formal interviews. First, we identify the key institutions and stakeholders in the Serbian VET context through document analysis of the law, the implementation plan, existing research on the Serbian VET system (i.e. Renold and Oswald-Egg, 2017), and informal interviews. We also use this process to identify the key moments in the implementation process. These serve as intermediary outcomes so we can measure progress. This process is complete as of this writing.

Second, we will identify a representative group of key stakeholders based on document analysis, including as many stakeholder types as possible. This is also complete. We are currently in the process of conducting formal interviews through in-country partners. These detect success factors and barriers to implementation. We will then analyze interview responses for trends based on the six-category framework of implementation success factors.

2.1 Document Analysis

The purpose of the document analysis step is to identify the critical institutions, stakeholders, and moments we should focus on during interviews. Table 1 summarizes the informal interviews and documents.

Table 1 Data summary for informal interviews and document analysis

Document/Source	Main Content
Informal Interviews	
Center of Education Policy (CEP)	Implementation plans, updates, Master Plan
Commission Article 40	Implementation plans and updates: Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development (MoESTD), Chamber of Commerce and Industry Serbia (CCIS), Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), German Society for International Cooperation (GIZ), German-Serbian Chamber of Commerce
International donors/partners	Implementation plans and updates: SDC, GIZ
Documents	
Dual VET Law	New law that dual VET shall be implemented in Serbia starting with the 2019-2020 cohort
Dual VET Imple-	Outlines specific actions, timelines, and actors' roles for

¹ http://www.un.org/en/development/desa/policy/wesp/wesp_current/2014wesp_country_classification.pdf

mentation Master Plan (versions through Nov. 2018)	dual VET implementation
Rulebook on Career Guidance and Counseling	Bylaw for career guidance and counseling
Rulebook on Instructor Training	Bylaw on training instructors that will support participants in the workplace
Rulebook on Student Placement	Bylaw on matching students with companies
KOF Education Systems Factbook: Serbia	Summary of the Serbian education and training system
Analysis of Challenges to Strengthening the Serbian Dual VET System	Report on pre-implementation concerns and possibilities

2.2 Interviews

Interviews are being carried out at the time of this writing with our partners at the Centre for Education Policy. Based on the results of the document analysis and informal interviews, Table 2 summarizes the interview subjects. There are a total of 220 subjects in categories of government, CCIS, trade unions, regional units, schools, companies, students, parents, and international partners. For the first four categories, the interview subjects represent the full population of actors in each type. For the latter categories, we select representatives.

Table 2 Interview subject plan

Institution	Interviewee(s)	Sample
Government		
MoESTD	Minister + 2 assistants in charge for secondary education and dual education	3
VET and Adult Education Council	President	1
Prime minister's office	Person in charge for dual education	1
Standing Conference of Cities and Municipalities	Representative commission member	1
Institute for improvement of education	Director	1
Chamber of Commerce and Industry Serbia		
N/A	President of CCIS	1
Centre for Education, Dual Education and Education Policies	Head of Centre	1
Centre for Support to Investments and Public Private Partnership	Head of Centre	1
Division for Providing Support in Representation and Protection of Members' Interests	Head of Division	1

Trade unions (labor)		
Branch union	President	1
Trade union with special focus on education issues	President	2
Trade union focused on labor issues	President	1
Regional units		
All 17 regional CCIS units	Directors	17
All 18 regional school administrations.	Heads	18
Schools		
Schools piloting dual VET since 2013/14 school year	School principals + Coordinators of Students' Professional Practice	3 +3 (~50%)
Schools involved in dual VET in 2017/18 school year	School principals + Coordinators of Students' Professional Practice	9 +9 (~10%)
Schools not involved in dual VET	School principals	20 (~10%)
Companies		
Companies involved in dual VET	Managers/HR directors	30 (5%)
Companies not involved in dual VET	Managers/HR directors	30
Students		
Students in dual VET in 2018/19	Students	30
Students in other VET profiles in 2018/19 school year.	Students	30
Parents		
Parents of children in dual VET	Parents	15
Parents of children not in dual VET	Parents	15
Donors and International Organizations		
Major donor org.s in dual VET	SDC, GIZ, ADA	3
Major international org.s in dual VET	EUD, ETF, UNICEF	3
TOTAL		220

Source: Centre for Education Policy

There are five schools that have been piloting dual VET models since 2013, 84 implementing in 2017/2018, and 247 schools not participating. All five pilot schools are sampled, plus nine new schools and 20 non-participating schools, representing regions appropriately. We interview 30 students each from the participating and non-participating groups of schools, out of the 2,969 in participating schools and 63,858 in non-participating schools. Similarly, we interview 15 parents from each group of schools.

Six hundred companies are currently involved in dual VET, and we sample 30 with consideration for regional variation and SME representation. We also interview 30 non-participating companies, with the same considerations for regions and size. Selection is a stratified random sample from the CCIS database.

2.3 Interview Analysis

Interviews will be finished in February of 2019. After translation into English, we will code the results using statistical analysis of the quantitative elements and three independent coders for the qualitative elements. Roughly, two-thirds of the questions in the interview contain data we can analyze quantitatively, with the remaining third open-ended. Interview questions address subjects' personal and institutional background, their awareness of the new dual VET law, context fit, magnitude and type of changes required, willingness to participate, ability to participate, expectations for cooperation and coordination, opinions about their own and other actors' political will, and detailed questions about history with dual VET and specific bylaws.

3 Results

At this point, we have already carried out the document analysis. Part of the results of that process is the interview form and subject list, but we also identified critical moments in the implementation process. Figure 2 summarizes the critical path from October 2018 to the program's first full implementation in September of 2019. There are already five pilot schools that have been running dual VET programs since 2013, and 84 that implemented in the 2017/18 school year. For the 2019 school year, the program needs to go to full implementation in all schools with implementation of the law and bylaws.

As shown in Figure 2, there are a number of new processes that need to be in place before implementation can begin, and many of them need to start long before the official program start. Career guidance and counseling should start according to the associated bylaw as soon as possible. Students cannot choose to participate without information. Similarly urgent is the establishment of a licensing body to certify training companies. Companies must be licensed before they can sign up with CCIS to host students. Once companies are engaged, they can sign a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with their local schools and regions can begin working with CCIS to develop proposed local enrollment plans.

Based on the local enrollment plans, MoESTD defines quotas, published after approval as the Call. Students take exams to place into programs, and then schools allocate them according to the Call. Once enrollment begins, schools match students to companies according to the bylaw. Finally, after all of those processes are completed—for the first time—the program begins.

Figure 2 Summary of critical implementation moments 2018-2019

Source: Authors' own depiction

There is a series of interdependent critical moments leading up to successful implementation, and the timeline is already quite tight. Based on interviews, we will be able to see how the process is going and what the main challenges and opportunities are. When there are major success factors and barriers, we will be able to identify them from interviewees' responses.

We expect to find that the fast timeline and missing attention to actors' incentives will delay implementation.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, we will present results from the first year of implementation (spring 2018-spring 2019). At this point, there are likely to be challenges unless the strategy (Content) is very clearly communicated and coordinated (Context). Political will and cooperation (Commitment) are both potential key factors, as are all members of the Capacity category. However, we expect that the items in Clients (Type) and Clients (Level) will be especially relevant at the start of the implementation process since high-level and government actors have been involved in formulating and refining the law for some time, but lower-level and employer actors will be new to the process.

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Note

This project is in collaboration with the Centre for Education Policy in Belgrade, Serbia.

Biographical notes

Katherine Caves is a postdoctoral researcher in the research center for comparative education systems at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH) in Zurich. She has a bachelor's degree from the University of California at Berkeley and earned her master's degree in the field of Education. Her PhD research was on the economics of education at the University of Zurich. Her research interests center around the economic, institutional, and infrastructure foundations of strong vocational education and training (VET) systems all over the world, especially what those foundations are in successful VET systems and how they can be developed in nascent VET systems. In addition to this project, she is currently working on identifying the success factors and barriers to labor market-oriented education systems reforms with the Center for the Economics and Management of Education and Training Systems (CEMETS).

Maria Esther Oswald-Egg is a researcher and doctoral student in the research center for comparative education systems at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH) in Zurich. She did her bachelor studies in Economics at the University of St. Gall Switzerland and graduated in 2010. For the master studies in Economics she moved to Zurich, Switzerland, and graduated in 2013 from the University of Zurich. Her dissertation area is in education economics and labor economics. Thereby, she focuses on the relation between the youth labor market and vocational education and training.